

PATTERNS OF ADAPTATION DISORDER DEVELOPMENT IN MEN WITH EARLY-STAGE CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

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ABSTRACT: Relevance. Adaptation disorders of the anxiety and depressive spectrum are common in patients with cardiovascular diseases and significantly influence disease course and quality of life. Purpose. To investigate the pathokinetic features of adaptation disorders in men with mild forms of cardiovascular disease. Materials and methods. A clinical and analytical study included men aged 30–60 years with stage I–II arterial hypertension or stable exertional angina (FC I–III), without myocardial infarction and with circulatory insufficiency \leq IIa. Clinical-psychopathological and statistical methods were applied. Results. The study involved 93 men with arterial hypertension (mean age 37,75 years) and 128 men with stable exertional angina (mean age 47.16 years). In hypertension, short-term anxiety reactions (35,94%) and mixed anxiety-depressive reactions (26,56%) prevailed. In angina, mixed anxiety-depressive reactions were most frequent (37,63%), followed by depressive reactions (25,81%). Anxiety affect predominated in depressive adaptation disorders in both groups. All patients received medical or non-pharmacological correction and were re-evaluated after two months. Conclusion. Adaptation disorders in men with mild cardiovascular disease demonstrate distinct pathokinetic features with a predominance of anxiety and depressive syndromes, highlighting the need for early diagnosis and individualized therapeutic approaches.

Key words: cardiovascular disease, anxiety, depression, mental retardation.

ПАТОКИНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ АДАПТАЦИОННЫХ РАССТРОЙСТВ У МУЖЧИН С ЛЕГКОЙ СТАДИЕЙ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ

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Аннотация: Актуальность. Адаптационные расстройства спектра тревоги и депрессии широко распространены у пациентов с сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями и оказывают значительное влияние на клиническое течение заболевания и качество жизни пациентов. Цель исследования. Изучение патокинетических особенностей адаптационных расстройств у мужчин с легкой стадией сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний. Материалы и методы. В исследование были включены мужчины в возрасте 30–60 лет с артериальной гипертензией I–II стадии или стабильной стенокардией напряжения (ФК I–III), без перенесенного инфаркта миокарда и с недостаточностью кровообращения \leq ПА. Применялись клинико-психопатологические и статистические методы. Результаты. В исследовании приняли участие 93 мужчины с артериальной гипертензией (средний возраст 37,75 лет) и 128 мужчин со стабильной стенокардией напряжения (средний возраст 47,16 лет). В группе с гипертензией преобладали кратковременные тревожные реакции (35,94%) и смешанные тревожно-депрессивные реакции (26,56%). В группе с стенокардией наибольшее распространение получили смешанные тревожно-депрессивные реакции (37,63%), затем депрессивные реакции (25,81%). В обеих группах при депрессивных адаптационных расстройствах преобладал тревожный аффект. Всем пациентам проводилась медикаментозная или немедикаментозная коррекция, повторная оценка состояния выполнена через два месяца. Вывод. Адаптационные расстройства у мужчин с легкой стадией сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний характеризуются специфическими патокинетическими особенностями с преобладанием тревожных и депрессивных синдромов, что подчеркивает необходимость ранней диагностики и индивидуализированного терапевтического подхода.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, тревога, депрессия, адаптационные расстройства.

ERKAKLARDA YENGIL BOSQICHLI QON-TOMIR KASALLIKLARIDA ADAPTATSIYA BUZILISHLARINING PATOKINETIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Dolzarblik. Xavotir va depressiya spektridagi adaptatsiya buzilishlari qon-tomir kasalliklari bo'lgan bemorlarda keng tarqalgan bo'lib, kasallikning klinik kechishi va bemorlarning hayot sifatiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi. Yengil bosqichli qon-tomir kasalliklari bo'lgan erkaklarda adaptatsiya buzilishlarining pathokinetik xususiyatlarini o'rganish. Materiallar va usullar. Tadqiqotga 30–60 yoshdagi, I–II bosqichli arterial gipertenziya yoki barqaror jismoniy kuchlanishli angina (FC I–III) bilan kasallangan, miokard infarkti bo'lmagan va qon aylanish yetishmovchiligi \leq IIA bo'lgan erkaklar kiritildi. Tadqiqotda kliniko-psixopatologik va statistik usullar qo'llanildi. Natijalar. Tadqiqotda 93 nafar arterial gipertenziya bilan kasallangan erkaklar (o'rtacha yosh 37,75 yil) va 128 nafar barqaror jismoniy kuchlanishli angina bilan kasallangan erkaklar (o'rtacha yosh 47,16 yil) ishtirok etdi. Gipertenziya guruhida qisqa muddatli xavotir reaksiyalari (35,94%) va aralash xavotir-depressiya reaksiyalari (26,56%) ustun bo'ldi. Angina guruhida esa aralash xavotir-depressiya reaksiyalari eng ko'p kuzatildi (37,63%), undan keyin depressiv reaksiyalar (25,81%) keladi. Ikkala guruhda ham depressiv adaptatsiya buzilishlarida xavotir ta'siri ustun bo'ldi. Barcha bemorlarga tibbiy yoki no-dori vositalari bilan korreksiya qilindi va ikki oy o'tgach qayta baholandi. Xulosa. Yengil bosqichli qon-tomir kasalliklari bo'lgan erkaklarda adaptatsiya buzilishlari o'ziga xos pathokinetik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, unda xavotir va depressiya sindromlari ustunlik qiladi. Bu esa erta tashxis va individual terapevtik yondashuvlarni qo'llash zarurligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: qon-tomir kasalliklari, xavotir, depressiya, ruhiy adaptatsiya buzilishi.

Introduction. As demonstrated in our earlier studies, human adaptive capacity, including adaptation to disease, depends not only on the functional state of the organism and its ability to respond adequately to adverse influences, but also on a complex of individual psychological traits and mechanisms of interpersonal interaction [1,2]. The significant role of mental adaptation in cardiovascular pathology, together with the high prevalence of its impairment, has led to the development of an independent interdisciplinary field-psychocardiology-integrating cardiology, psychology, and psychiatry [3].

This paper presents a concise overview of scientific data addressing the structural characteristics of mental maladaptation in patients with cardiovascular diseases, focusing on the dominant psychopathological manifestations observed in common forms of cardiac pathology [4].

Epidemiological evidence indicates a stable association between cardiovascular diseases and depressive disorders. In parallel, substantial data confirm the contribution of anxiety to the development and progression of cardiovascular pathology in the general population [5]. Clinical studies show that anxiety symptoms of clinical significance are observed in approximately one-third of patients with arterial hypertension and coronary artery disease, while depressive manifestations are detected in nearly 30-38% of cases [6].

Psychopathological symptoms in cardiovascular patients have been shown to correlate with unfavorable social and behavioral factors, including low educational level, insufficient income, reduced physical activity, chronic psycho-emotional stress, exposure to acute stressors, social isolation, and inadequate social support. These factors are often accompanied by elevated blood pressure and increased

utilization of healthcare services [7]. The presence of clinically significant depression during initial assessment is associated with a higher risk of adverse cardiovascular outcomes, including non-fatal and fatal events.

Large-scale studies involving patients with coronary heart disease revealed high stress levels in more than half of the examined cohort, while depressive symptoms of varying severity were identified in the majority of both men and women. Clinically significant anxiety disorders were diagnosed in over 40% of patients, with no statistically significant gender differences. Overall, approximately one in four patients with coronary artery disease requires specialized psychological or psychiatric intervention [8-11].

Numerous international studies confirm that depressive disorders represent a substantial independent risk factor for the development of coronary artery disease and serve as a predictor of coronary mortality [12]. Disorders of the depressive spectrum are detected in a considerable proportion of patients during the early period following acute myocardial infarction, with anxiety-depressive reactions and other affective disorders forming a significant part of the clinical structure. During long-term follow-up, the prevalence of depressive spectrum disorders demonstrates a tendency to increase [13-16].

Depressive disorders in cardiovascular pathology are characterized by marked clinical heterogeneity, pronounced somatovegetative symptoms, and diverse psychopathological manifestations, which significantly complicate the clinical course of cardiovascular diseases. A persistent combination of anxiety, depressive symptoms, and autonomic dysfunction is commonly observed in the structure of affective disorders in patients with cardiovascular disease [17-20].

The purpose of the study: Analysis of adaptation disorder dynamics in men with early-stage cardiovascular pathology.

Materials and research methods: The study included men aged 30-60 years diagnosed with mild forms of cardiovascular pathology, including stage I-II arterial hypertension with grades 1-3 blood pressure elevation, a cardiovascular risk level not exceeding 3, and circulatory insufficiency up to stage IIA, as well as stable exertional angina of functional classes I-III without a history of myocardial infarction. Clinical-psychopathological assessment and statistical analysis methods were applied.

Results and their discussion: Two cohorts of male patients diagnosed with arterial hypertension or stable exertional angina and presenting with adaptation disorders of the anxiety and/or depressive spectrum were examined. The first cohort comprised 93 men with arterial hypertension and adaptation disorders, with a mean age of 37,75 years. The second cohort included 128 men with stable exertional angina pectoris, with an average age of 47,16 years.

In the group of patients with arterial hypertension, the clinical and psychopathological structure of adaptation disorders was characterized by short-term anxiety reactions in 46 cases (35,94%), prolonged anxiety reactions in 25 cases (19,53%), mixed anxiety-depressive reactions in 34 patients (26,56%), and depressive reactions of varying duration in 23 patients (17,97%).

Among patients with stable exertional angina, mixed anxiety-depressive reactions were most frequently observed, affecting 35 individuals (37,63%). Depressive reactions were identified in 24 patients (25,81%), while short-term anxiety reactions occurred in 19 cases (20,43%), and prolonged anxiety reactions in 15 cases (16,13%).

Analysis of the leading affective component in adaptation disorders with predominant depressive symptoms demonstrated a clear dominance of anxiety affect in both patient groups, accounting for 66,67% in men with arterial hypertension and 73,91% in those with stable exertional angina. Sad affect was

observed less frequently (29,17% and 21,74%, respectively), while apathetic affect was rare in both groups (4,16% and 4,35%).

All participants underwent pharmacological or non-pharmacological correction of adaptation disorders for a two-week period. A follow-up assessment conducted two months later included all patients from both cohorts.

Catamnestic observation revealed several characteristic patterns in the pathokinesis of adaptation disorders: (1) rapid and often complete symptom regression following favorable changes in psychosocial circumstances or timely and adequate therapeutic intervention; (2) recurrence of psychopathological manifestations according to a stereotypical pattern in response to new traumatic stressors, leading to a prolonged course with expansion and stabilization of clinical symptoms; and (3) transformation of adaptation disorders into neurotic, affective, endogenous, or addictive mental disorders.

In the majority of cases (81,63%), adaptation disorders did not undergo transformation. Neurotic manifestations were observed in 9,19% of patients, addictive disorders (primarily alcohol dependence) in 4,08%, and endogenous mental disorders in 5,1%.

When depressive symptoms predominated, transformation of adaptation disorders occurred in 33,85% of cases, including progression to subclinical endogenous affective manifestations in 18,46% and initial stages of depressive episodes in 15,39%. Mixed anxiety-depressive adaptation disorders transformed in 17,71% of cases, with subsequent development of affective, anxiety-phobic, panic, or addictive disorders. Adaptation disorders dominated by anxiety symptoms progressed in 11,28% of patients, most frequently resulting in anxiety-phobic conditions and addictive disorders.

Thus, adaptation disorders with predominant depressive symptoms tend to evolve toward endogenous affective pathology, anxiety-dominant forms are more often associated with anxiety-phobic and addictive disorders, while mixed forms demonstrate a broader spectrum of psychopathological transformations.

The most pronounced transformation of adaptation disorders was observed in cases dominated by depressive symptomatology, accounting for 33,85% of observations. In contrast, adaptation disorders characterized primarily by anxiety symptoms demonstrated the lowest transformation rate at 11,28%, while mixed anxiety-depressive forms occupied an intermediate position, occurring in 17,71% of cases.

During the analysis, several prognostically unfavorable indicators of transformation in adaptation disorders were identified. These included the predominance of sad or emotionally indifferent affect in depressive reactions, prolonged duration of maladaptive states, the presence of sensitive and asthenoneurotic premorbid personality traits, disruption of the direct temporal relationship between psychotraumatic events and the onset or progression of symptoms (particularly in neurotic manifestations), as well as reduced patient initiative and passivity in coping with ongoing stressors.

Furthermore, catamnestic follow-up revealed that sustained stabilization of cardiovascular disease outcomes was documented in more than half of the patients in Group 1 (58,11%, n = 86). In the second subgroup, stable treatment effects were observed in 38,36% of patients (n = 28), while in the third subgroup, this indicator was noted in 20,55% of cases (n = 28).

Conclusions. In conclusion, the present study made it possible to determine specific features of the pathokinetic development of adaptation disorders and to identify prognostically unfavorable factors associated with their transformation. Recognition of these indicators may contribute to improving the effectiveness and quality of medical and psychological care provided to this group of patients.

The psychopathological profile of patients with arterial hypertension is characterized by a combination of neurotic and neurosis-like disorders. Syndrome analysis revealed a predominance of depressive manifestations (55,8%), followed by anxiety syndromes (15,8%), hypochondriacal features (12,5%), hysterical manifestations (10,8%), and obsessive-phobic symptoms (5%).

A generalized assessment of mental maladaptation in cardiovascular diseases indicates a high prevalence of affective spectrum disorders, primarily presenting with anxiety and depressive symptoms, often accompanied by hypochondriacal components. The development of mental maladaptation appears to be closely related to stress exposure, individual personality traits, and psychosocial determinants.

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